

Microwave Assisted Alternate Synthesis Of A Series Of Azomethine Derivatives Of A Semisynthetic Aminopenicillin (Ampicillin)

Abhilash Mullasseril

Mullasseril, veliyanad post., ernakulam dist., kerala-682 313, India.

*Corresponding author: E-mail: mabhilash@hotmail.com

Received: May 22, 2015, Accepted: June 28, 2015, Published: June 28, 2015.

ABSTRACT

The field of synthesis of organic compounds having medicinal importance is in a state of boom developments and it always incorporates different possible methods for achieving the target drugs and similar compounds. All the methods adopted for synthesis of pharmaceuticals must be routed firmly to the green principles in a maximum possible manner. This paper aims the microwave assisted synthesis of a series of azomethine derivatives of widely prescribing semisynthetic penicillin drug called ampicillin. The microwave assisted synthesis of organic compounds is considered as one of the safest among green methods of the synthesis. For the synthesis of azomethines a series of aromatic aldehydes with varying substituent groups and the drug ampicillin trihydrate were irradiated using microwave as the source of energy for the synthesis.

Keywords: Ampicillin; MWAOS; Computer aided Drug designing; Biological activity; Computational methods; Docking

INTRODUCTION

The field of drug research is always introduces interesting novel methods for the synthesis of drug or drug like molecules and microwave heating is the superior among other methods [1,2]. The scientists are giving more attention recently to the use of microwave ovens for the organic synthesis supported by the increasing number of papers found in the available scientific literature. Presently many researchers and groups of many universities and institutions are found actively engaged in MWAOS and publishing many mind blowing results. In electromagnetic spectra the Microwaves have wavelengths of 1mm-1m, corresponding to frequencies between 0.3 and 300GHz. In order to avoid interference, the wavelength at which the industrial and domestic microwave apparatus intended for heating operations is regulated generally to 12.2cm, corresponding to a frequency of 2.450(+/- 0.050)GHz as we observe from the manuals. Even though the heating power of microwaves has been known for quite a long time its usage in pharmaceutical research started very recently and this microwave technology has been used since the late 1970s, in inorganic chemistry but it has only been implemented in organic chemistry since the mid-1980s and now became a widely using research technique of green chemistry as evident from the scientific literatures. It could be due to its lack of controllability and reproducibility faced during the synthesis along with many safety aspects and a generally low degree of understanding of the basics of dielectric heating of microwaves that is introduced into the chemical reactor remotely which has a direct access to the reaction control as it being the main energy source applied to the reaction vessel. The microwave radiation passes through the walls of the reaction vessel and heats only the reactants and solvents in a uniform manner throughout the reaction and causes lesser byproducts. The reduced possibility of byproducts formation made it one of the greener methods with a prime importance. Microwaves also simplified many complicated methods and reduced the use of many solvents and also triggered

techniques like solvent free organic synthesis. The power of microwave techniques have now been realized in various synthetic operations such as protection and deprotection, condensation, oxidation, reduction, cyclization, rearrangement reactions and rapid synthesis of heterocyclic system on solid supports [3]. Many of the scientists are trying to redesign the methods of synthesis, the most attracting field of chemistry to more environmentally benign approaches by adopting many plausible worth concepts of green chemistry. There are many available reviews and research papers on MWAOS in the present scientific literatures claim various biological importance to the synthesized drug like derivatives (like Schiff bases and β -lactams) at the amino group [4a-d]. The drug resistance is one of the most challenging problems that faced by the drug researchers all over the world. The easiest remedy for overcoming this hurdle is the suitable derivatisation of the presently prescribing drugs [5]. In this paper simple microwave assisted synthesis of derivatives of a leadingly prescribing aminopenicillin namely ampicillin are proposed and synthesized (Scheme 1).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used for this synthesis were a series of substituted aromatic aldehydes (Sigma Aldrich make) and the drug ampicillin trihydrate (physician's sample of various make). The reactants were used as such without any further purification. The usages of purified solvents were limited to a possible minimum. The experimental techniques were carried out in a domestic microwave oven of (Samsung make). Computational methods were carried out in on a Windows Vista Business based system with Genuine Intel (R) CPU T2050 1.60GHz 512 MB of memory. Molecular modelling was achieved by MOPAC and docking studies were carried out in ArgusLab4.0.1 as reported earlier. The antibacterial studies of the compounds were carried out and found comparable to the earlier reported paper [6].

EXPERIMENTAL

D1S1 is	R ¹ =OH	R ² =R ³ =R ⁴ =R ⁵ =H
D1S2 is	R ¹ =NO ₂	R ² =R ³ =R ⁴ =R ⁵ =H
D1S3 is	R ² =NO ₂	R ¹ =R ³ =R ⁴ =R ⁵ =H
D1S4 is	R ² =N(CH ₃) ₂	R ¹ =R ³ =R ⁴ =R ⁵ =H
D1S5 is	R ² =OH; R ⁴ =O(CH ₃)	R ¹ =R ³ =R ⁵ =H
	And	
D1S6 is	R ³ =OH	R ¹ =R ² =R ⁴ =R ⁵ =H

The equimolar mixture of the drug (ampicillin) and the aromatic aldehyde mixed thoroughly in a glass mortar. It is moistened with basic methanol and transferred to a 25mL glass beaker immersed on a silica bath and irradiated with microwave. The changes were recorded and the irradiations were stopped immediately when visible colour change appeared. The time needed for the derivative formation varies with different starting materials. The derivatives obtained were cooled and crushed in a mortar and further purified

using common methods. The systematic characterizations of the synthesized derivatives were carried out by UV, FT-IR and NMR. The results were compared with theoretically predicted results of computational studies of various methods like AM1, MNDO, MNDO/3 and PM3.

Scheme 1: Various derivatives of the drug prepared by Microwave irradiation method.

The drug and its different derivatives of the drugs were coded as D1, D1S1, D1S2, D1S3, D1S4, D1S5 and D1S6 for easy usage in the common parlance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO-D₆ and found much complicated to interpret completely but the shift of NH proton attached to the lactam ring was found to be more and more deshielded and shifts to higher δ-values in all the derivatives than parent drug. The -NH₂ protons were found absent in the derivatives and the deshielded -N=CH protons in the derivative are clearly observed in higher δ-values [6]. All the spectra were showing characteristic peaks of COOH around 9-10ppm and vanished in presence of few drops of D₂O. The predicted vibration spectral (infra red) data using different computational methods like AM1, MNDO, MNDO/3 and PM3 were comparable with the actual spectral data observed (Table 1).

Table 1: Calculated and plausibly assigned vibrational frequencies of drug and its derivatives.

Derivative	Functional Group	Vibrational Frequency Calculated and Observed and Assigned (CM ⁻¹)					
		AM1	MNDO	MNDO/3	PM3	Average	Observed
Drug (Ampicillin)	NH ₂ and NH	3345.23	3471.25	3483.98	3446.23	3436.67	3449
	C=O LACT.	2021.04	2099.73	1833.97	1950.95	1976.42	2089
	C=O	1965.19	2043.10	1823.61	1911.86	1935.94	1774
D1S1	OH and NH	3455.59	3989.36	3953.49	3408.68	3701.78	3205
	N=C	2017.43	1987.72	2006.07	2043.05	2013.57	2009
	C=O LACT.	2025.61	2120.40	1844.39	1966.73	1989.28	1799
	C=O	1963.35	2059.44	1829.56	1953.33	1951.42	1674
D1S2	OH carboxyl	3417.93	3959.61	3736.34	3419.62	3633.38	3342
	N=C	1921.04	1995.83	2183.05	2038.28	2034.55	1524
	C=O LACT.	2017.52	2104.58	1756.04	1966.67	1961.20	1730
	C=O	1974.31	2065.90	1720.05	1952.58	1928.21	1642
D1S3	OH carboxyl	3421.58	3763.72	3932.02	3858.97	3744.07	3289
	N=C	2069.85	2068.59	1927.19	1906.68	1993.08	1608
	C=O LACT.	2261.05	2330.36	2021.20	2073.07	2171.42	1773
	C=O	1966.80	2004.23	1843.50	1926.00	1935.13	1664
D1S4	OH carboxyl	3423.17	3962.52	3965.33	3835.77	3796.70	3204
	N=C	2058.72	1994.19	1775.84	1834.77	1915.88	2098
	C=O LACT.	2271.52	2321.73	2054.80	2096.08	2186.03	1793
	C=O	1991.56	2083.47	1796.05	1922.22	1948.33	1773
D1S5	OH carboxyl	3448.54	3981.05	3978.69	3828.61	3809.22	3225
	N=C	1994.82	1966.23	1755.91	1839.71	1889.17	1589
	C=O LACT.	2117.57	2218.65	1936.52	2094.69	2091.86	1740
	C=O	2014.76	2088.02	1820.84	1920.02	1960.91	1670
D1S6	OH carboxyl	3451.72	3970.77	3955.04	3884.91	3815.61	3205

	N=C	1995.22	1950.72	1915.66	1901.92	1940.88	1581
	C=O LACT.	2117.69	2208.46	2010.42	2073.78	2102.59	1774
	C=O	2010.02	2089.93	1845.32	1929.61	1968.72	1674

The observed differences from the observed and calculated results may be due to the limitations of the present workstation used. As expected the AM1 method was the suitable one for the prediction of vibrational spectra as claimed by the inventors. The observed data were found comparable with the reported compounds synthesized earlier through the conventional methods [6].

CONCLUSION

The molecular modeling was achieved using standard software and accepted methods. The insilico QSAR studies of the derivatives were performed as per accepted methods and reported as earlier [6]. All the derivatives under study are obeying the Lipinski rules of 5 for modern definition for drugs and hence are promising [7]. The synthesized derivatives were found comparable to the reported derivatives prepared under conventional methods from their characterization. The activities of drug derivatives were found in accordance to the docking values and also showed comparable antibacterial studies with slight variation in activities from the conventionally prepared derivatives. The present studies supported that the microwave assisted methods can also be adopted for synthesis of suitable derivatives that have pharmacological importance with acceptable therapeutic values.

Citation: Abhilash Mullasseril et al (2015), Microwave Assisted Alternate Synthesis Of A Series Of Azomethine Derivatives Of A Semisynthetic Aminopenicillin (Ampicillin). J. of Modern Drug Discovery and Drug Delivery Research. V3I1. DOI: 10.15297/JMDDR.V3I1.01

Copyright: © 2015 Abhilash Mullasseril. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

REFERENCES

1. Krstenansky, J.L.; Cotterill, I. Current Opinion in Drug Discovery & Development.2000, 4, 454.
2. Larhed, M.; Hallberg, A. Drug Discovery Today. 2001, 6, 406.
3. Mavandadi, F.; Pilotti, A. Drug Discovery Today.2006, 11, 165.
4. For recent reviews on microwave-assisted organic synthesis see:
Kappe, C.O.; Angew.Chem.Int.Ed.2004, 43, 6250.
Kappe, C.O.; Dallinger, D. Nat. Drug. Disc. Rev.2006, 5, 51.
Nagariya, A.K.; et al. Journal of pharmacy Research. 2010, 3, 575.
Jignasa, K.S.; et al. Der Pharma Chemica. 2010, 2(1), 342.
5. More, D.H.; et al. PPJournal of Scientific & Industrial Research.2003, 62, 1024.
6. Mullasseril, A.; WJPPS. 2014, 3(4), 1082.
7. Lipinski, C.A.; Drug Discovery Today: Technologies. 2004, 1(4), 337.